

Review

Research on the Effectiveness and Methodology of Acupuncture for Ankle Sprain – A Preliminary Systematic Review.

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Abstract: Background: Ankle sprains are a common musculoskeletal injury associated with significant pain, functional impairment, and high recurrence rates. Conventional treatments often combine pharmacological, physical, and rehabilitative strategies. Acupuncture, rooted in Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM), is increasingly recognized for its potential therapeutic role, though its clinical effectiveness for ankle sprains requires further examination.

Objective: To make a preliminary systematic review of randomized controlled trials (RCTs) evaluating the efficacy of acupuncture in the treatment of ankle sprains, with a focus on methodological approaches and point selection.

Methods: A systematic search was conducted across PubMed, EuropePMC, and SciELO databases (inception–March 2025) using the keywords: (ankle sprain) AND (acupuncture) AND (randomized controlled trial). Inclusion criteria: RCTs involving human participants with ankle sprains, published in English, Chinese, Spanish, French, or Portuguese, evaluating acupuncture interventions. Data extraction focused on study design, interventions, comparators, outcomes, and acupuncture point selection.

Results: Eight studies comprising 604 participants met the inclusion criteria. Interventions included conventional acupuncture (6 studies), electro-acupuncture (1), and acupuncture with moxibustion (1). Acupuncture demonstrated consistent efficacy in reducing pain, improving function, and enhancing proprioception, often comparable to or exceeding standard therapies such as physiotherapy or pharmacotherapy. Commonly used points included ST41, GB40, and BL60. Localized techniques (e.g., surrounding needling), distal systemic points (e.g., LI4, LV3), and individualized *Ashi* points were employed depending on the injury stage and symptom presentation.

Conclusion: Acupuncture appears to be an effective and well-tolerated intervention for ankle sprains, showing promise in both acute care and rehabilitation. Strategic point selection and adjunctive methods may enhance outcomes. Despite encouraging findings, further high-quality RCTs are warranted to confirm efficacy.

Keywords: Acupuncture; Traditional Chinese Medicine; Ankle Sprain; Musculoskeletal Injury; Proprioception; Rehabilitation.

Citation: Azevedo R., Querido S., Santoro A., Caneiras R., Gomes B., Serra E., Torres R. Research on the Effectiveness and Methodology of Acupuncture for Ankle Sprain – A Preliminary Systematic Review. *Journal of Complementary Therapies in Health*. 2025;3(1) 10.5281/zenodo.15284256

Academic Editor: Jorge Rodrigues

Received: 17 March 2025

Reviewed: 12 April 2025

Accepted: 19 April 2025

Published: 25 April 2025

Publisher's Note: IPTC stays neutral with regard to jurisdictional claims in published maps and institutional affiliations.

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1. Introduction

Sprains represent a substantial public health burden, characterized by their high incidence and the consequent decline in affected individuals' quality of life ¹. The clinical presentation of sprains, varying with severity and location, typically includes acute pain, localized inflammation, oedema, ecchymosis, restricted range of motion, and potential

joint misalignment. In severe cases, joint instability, heightened tenderness, and functional impairment may manifest²⁻⁴. Furthermore, complications arising from sprains and muscle injuries can lead to both transient and enduring disabilities, resulting in functional and socioeconomic limitations for affected individuals^{1,4-6}.

Musculoskeletal injuries, including sprains, are influenced by a variety of factors, encompassing age, inadequate warm-up routines, participation in contact sports, and genetic predispositions⁷⁻⁹. A comprehensive diagnostic process for sprains necessitates a thorough patient history, a detailed physical examination, and often, supplementary imaging. Radiography is invaluable for assessing joint structural integrity and identifying fractures, while ultrasound and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) offers detailed visualization of soft tissue structures, such as muscles, tendons, and ligaments¹⁰⁻¹⁴.

Specifically, acute ankle sprains represent a prevalent musculoskeletal injury, particularly among individuals engaged in physical activities^{15,16}. Furthermore, these sprains exhibit a high recurrence rate, contributing to the development of chronic ankle instability^{16,17}. Preventive interventions centred on musculoskeletal strengthening, balance, proprioceptive training, and biomechanical optimization have demonstrated significant benefits in mitigating lower extremity musculoskeletal injuries and facilitating recovery from pain and dysfunction in targeted populations^{18,19}.

Conventional treatment strategies for sprains typically involve a multidisciplinary approach, prioritizing pain alleviation, inflammation reduction, tissue healing promotion, and functional restoration. This may include pharmacological management with analgesics and anti-inflammatory agents, physiotherapy for muscle strengthening, flexibility enhancement, and functional rehabilitation, temporary joint immobilization using splints or bandages, and, in severe cases, surgical interventions to repair damaged anatomical structures²⁰⁻²². However, it is crucial to acknowledge that the scope of research evaluating the efficacy of certain interventions remains limited, despite promising preliminary findings²³. Given the high incidence of recurrent ankle sprains, chronic ankle instability, and their association with posttraumatic osteoarthritis, the development and evaluation of secondary and tertiary prevention strategies are imperative to decrease the prevalence of these conditions²³.

Traditional Chinese medicine (TCM), a system of healthcare refined over millennia²⁴⁻²⁸, posits that health is contingent upon the harmonious balance of the body's interconnected systems. Disruptions in this equilibrium can manifest as illness²⁸⁻³². The integration of TCM therapies into conventional Western medicine practices reflects a growing trend towards integrative medicine, recognizing the potential synergistic benefits of both approaches³³⁻⁴².

Acupuncture, a TCM technique involving the insertion of fine needles into specific anatomical points^{37,43,44}, has gained recognition as a valuable therapeutic modality for various health conditions⁴⁵⁻⁴⁸. Its mechanism of action is thought to involve the modulation of the nervous, endocrine, exocrine, and circulatory systems, fostering optimal health⁴⁹. In the context of musculoskeletal injuries, acupuncture may contribute to pain reduction, inflammation mitigation, enhanced local blood flow, muscle spasm relief, and tissue regeneration^{50,51}.

Therefore, the goal of this study is to conduct a comprehensive review of the available evidence on the use of acupuncture for ankle sprains, with a focus on its effectiveness and methodology.

2. Methodology

2.1. Search Strategy

A literature search was performed to identify randomized controlled trials (RCTs) assessing the efficacy of acupuncture in the treatment of ankle sprains. A comprehensive search strategy was developed and implemented across multiple electronic databases, including PubMed, EuropePMC, and SciELO, covering the period from database inception

to March 2025. The search strategy utilized the following Boolean operators: (Ankle sprain) AND (acupuncture) AND (randomized controlled trial).

2.1. Eligibility Criteria

This review included RCTs investigating the effect of acupuncture on ankle sprains in human participants. Studies were eligible for inclusion if they: (1) involved participants with a diagnosis of ankle sprain; (2) were published in English, Chinese, Spanish, French, or Portuguese; (3) evaluated any form of acupuncture as an intervention; and (4) reported ankle sprain-related outcomes. Studies involving animal subjects or those lacking an acupuncture intervention were excluded.

3. Results

A total of 34 records were identified through database searches. After removing 11 duplicates, 23 records remained for screening. Of these, 13 were excluded.

Ten full-text reports were sought for retrieval, with one report not retrieved. Among the nine reports assessed for eligibility, one was excluded for using the wrong study design. Ultimately, eight studies met the inclusion criteria and were included in the systematic review.

Figure 1 provides detailed information about the selection process

Eight studies involving 604 participants were included. All studies evaluated various acupuncture-based interventions for ankle sprain or related conditions, with sample sizes ranging from 30 to 166 participants.

Conventional acupuncture was the most frequently applied technique, used in 6 studies ⁵²⁻⁵⁷. Electro-acupuncture and conventional acupuncture with moxibustion were each used in 1 study ^{58,59}.

Several techniques were used as comparators, namely physiotherapy ^{58,59}, micro-needle knife therapy ⁵², kinesiotape ⁵³, tendon regulation manipulation ⁵⁴, cold compression ⁵⁵, pharmacotherapy ⁵⁶, and tuina ⁵⁷.

A summary of the characteristics of the included studies is provided in Table 1.

Table 1. Characteristics of the included studies.

Study	Acupuncture technique	Sample	Comparators
Lu <i>et al.</i> ⁵²	Conventional acupuncture	80 patients	Micro-needle knife therapy
Shin <i>et al.</i> ⁵³	Conventional acupuncture	60 patients	Kinesiotape + acupuncture
Du <i>et al.</i> ⁵⁴	Conventional acupuncture	60 patients	Tendon regulation manipulation or tendon regulation manipulation + <i>Xiaojie</i>
Zhang <i>et al.</i> ⁵⁵	Conventional acupuncture	68 patients	Cold compression
Cohen <i>et al.</i> ⁵⁶	Conventional acupuncture	528 patients (166 with ankle sprain)	Pharmacotherapy or Pharmacotherapy + acupuncture
Yang <i>et al.</i> ⁵⁷	Conventional acupuncture	90 chronic sprain patients	Tuina
Tang <i>et al.</i> ⁵⁸	Conventional acupuncture with moxibustion	30 athletes	Physiotherapy
Zhu <i>et al.</i> ⁵⁹	Electro-acupuncture	50 athletes	Physiotherapy

4. Effectiveness of acupuncture for ankle sprain

The findings from the reviewed studies underscore the clinical effectiveness of acupuncture and related interventions in the treatment of ankle sprains, with consistent evidence supporting their role in reducing pain, improving joint function, and enhancing proprioception. However, differences in treatment modalities, outcome measures, and follow-up periods warrant a nuanced interpretation of the results.

Lu *et al.* ⁵² demonstrated that both acupuncture and micro-needle knife therapy significantly improved pain and function without adverse events. Notably, micro-needle knife therapy exhibited superior short-term efficacy in releasing superficial fascia at the intermediate time point, although this advantage was not sustained by the final assessment. This suggests a potentially faster onset of action with micro-needle therapy, while long-term outcomes may converge across modalities. Although both TCM techniques were comparable in efficacy, acupuncture emerges as a less invasive approach that does not require any kind of anaesthetic before intervention.

In the randomized study by Shin *et al.* ⁵³, both acupuncture and the combination of acupuncture with kinesiotaping led to significant improvements in pain, function, and quality of life. However, no statistically significant differences were observed between groups, including in subgroup analyses based on symptom severity. These findings highlight the comparable efficacy of acupuncture-based therapies and suggest that adjunct techniques may not offer additional benefits in all cases.

Du *et al.* ⁵⁴ compared the use of *Xiaojie* point manipulation, tendon-regulation therapy and both techniques combined. The authors reported high effectiveness across all treatment groups, with a notably higher curative rate in the combined therapy group. Reductions in pain and symptom scores were more pronounced in the combined and *Xiaojie* point manipulation groups compared to tendon-regulation therapy. These findings support the additive effects of integrative treatment strategies, particularly in alleviating pain and swelling.

Similarly, Zhang *et al.*⁵⁵ compared the use of the combination of surrounding acupuncture needling and cold compression to cold compression alone. It was found that while both groups experienced significant improvements in pain and ankle function, the combined therapy group achieved superior outcomes. The observed benefits at both early (3-day) and later (1-week) time points underscore the potential value of multimodal interventions during the acute phase of recovery.

In the study of Cohen *et al.*⁵⁶, significant functional improvements were observed in all groups, including acupuncture, pharmacotherapy, and their combination, with no significant differences between them. These results suggest that acupuncture may be as effective as conventional pharmacological treatment in the early management of ankle sprains, offering a potentially valuable non-pharmacologic alternative.

Yang *et al.*⁵⁷ further emphasized the efficacy of individualized or combination-enhanced interventions. The combination group was exposed to an acupuncture plus tuina massage intervention while the control group received tuina massage only. The combination of both techniques demonstrated superior outcomes in pain reduction during running, lower pain at rest, and higher patient satisfaction. These findings add strength to the idea that tailoring treatment components may enhance therapeutic outcomes.

Proprioceptive recovery, a critical component in ankle sprain rehabilitation, was addressed by Tang *et al.*⁵⁸ and Zhu *et al.*⁵⁹. Both studies reported significant improvements in joint position sense following acupuncture and electroacupuncture respectively, with outcomes superior to those observed in physiotherapy groups. These findings indicate a potential advantage of acupuncture over physiotherapy in restoring neuromuscular control and preventing recurrent injury.

Although systematic reviews^{60,61} previously lacked sufficient high-quality evidence to endorse acupuncture, more recent systematic reviews^{62,63} support its potential therapeutic benefit for patients with acute ankle sprain, which is in agreement with the results of the present research.

5. Analysis of Acupuncture Point Selection Across Studies

The reviewed studies employed a range of acupuncture points for the treatment of ankle sprains, primarily combining local points near the injury site with distal or systemic points aimed at broader physiological effects such as pain modulation and circulation enhancement. Most techniques used conventional acupuncture, with only one study applying electroacupuncture and another incorporating moxibustion.

According to the data provided in Table 2., several acupuncture points emerged as commonly selected for ankle sprain, particularly ST41 (*Jiexi*) which was used in 6 studies, GB40 (*Qiuxu*) and BL60 (*Kunlun*) which were used in 5 studies.

Table 2. Acupuncture points used in the included studies.

Study	Acupuncture points
Lu <i>et al.</i> ⁵²	Points: GB39, BL60, BL40, ST41, KI9, and KI6.
Shin <i>et al.</i> ⁵³	Points: ST36, ST41, BL60, BL62, KI3, KI6, GB39, and GB40
Du <i>et al.</i> ⁵⁴	Points: Xiaojie
Zhang <i>et al.</i> ⁵⁵	Points: Surrounding needling
Cohen <i>et al.</i> ⁵⁶	Points: LI4 and LV3 Local points would be selected from: ST41, GB40, BL60, BL62, BL63; or BL64 KI2, KI3, KI6, SP4, SP5. Distal points: SP6, SP9, GB34, ST36, and HT7 on the opposite wrist. Other points: <i>Ashi</i> points as suitable.
Yang <i>et al.</i> ⁵⁷	Points: BL62/KI6, ST41/LR4, and GB40/SP5. Other points: 2 <i>Ashi</i> points as suitable.
Tang <i>et al.</i> ⁵⁸	Points: GB40, BL60, BL62, and ST41.

	Other points: <i>Ashi</i> points around the injury site.
Zhu <i>et al.</i> ⁵⁹	Points: ST41, BL60 and GB40. Other points: <i>Ashi</i> points as suitable.

BL62 (*Shenmai*) and KI6 (*Zhaohai*) were also frequently used (4 studies), while GB39 (*Xuanzhong*) was used less often (2 studies).

All these points are anatomically relevant to the ankle region as they are located near the lateral malleolus and Achilles tendon, frequently involved in ankle sprain injuries ⁶⁴. Their frequent selection suggests a consensus around their local effectiveness for reducing inflammation, relieving pain, and supporting tissue healing.

Also important to note, several studies ⁵⁶⁻⁵⁹ employed *Ashi* points, or points of tenderness/pain identified through palpation. This approach allows for individualized treatment based on specific patient pathology and aligns with TCM principles ⁶⁵. *Ashi* points are particularly useful in musculoskeletal injuries due to their capacity to localize qi and blood stasis ⁶⁶⁻⁶⁸.

However, some studies included the use of distal and systemic points. For example, LI4 (*Hegu*) and LV3 (*Taichong*), called the “four gates” are traditionally used for systemic circulation and pain relief and neuroimaging studies of this combination are being conducted ⁶⁹⁻⁷². Other examples are SP6, SP9, ST36, and GB34, which are being studied for their regulatory distal effects ⁷³⁻⁸¹. This broader approach may reflect an attempt to balance local treatment with systemic support, especially useful in more chronic or severe cases.

Some other examples may be the use of HT7 (*Shenmen*) in the contralateral wrist of the affected ankle. This is a classic approach already mentioned in the ancient classic of the Yellow Emperor ⁸² which states that this technique is one of the nine “needling techniques to treat the nine types of pathological conditions(...) the eighth technique is the counterpart puncture, for the disease of the left, pricking the acupuncture point of the right, and vice versa” ⁸³. Indeed, functional magnetic resonance imaging studies demonstrate that contralateral acupuncture elicits specific brain activation and connectivity patterns ⁸⁴⁻⁸⁶, potentially explaining its therapeutic benefits.

Meanwhile, specific approaches were also employed in some studies. Zhang *et al.* ⁵⁵ used surrounding needling (also called “Surrounding the Dragon” or *Wei Ci*), a local technique targeting the injury perimeter, emphasizing direct modulation of inflammation and soft tissue healing ⁸⁷⁻⁸⁹. On the other hand, Du *et al.* ⁵⁴ focused on the Xiaojie point, less commonly reported in mainstream acupuncture literature. This point is located in the LU channel between LU10 and LU11, at the junction of the 1st metacarpal bone and the distal phalangeal segment of the thumb, and is specifically indicated for ankle sprain ^{90,91}.

Also, electroacupuncture Zhu *et al.* ⁵⁹ and moxibustion Tang *et al.* ⁵⁸ were used adjunctively to stimulate points more intensely or provide warmth, respectively, which may enhance blood flow and neuromuscular recovery ⁹²⁻⁹⁴.

Regarding the injury stage, there appears to be a trend toward more local point use in acute settings (e.g., Lu *et al.* ⁵², Zhang *et al.* ⁵⁵), while distal points and systemic strategies (e.g., Cohen *et al.* ⁵⁶) were more common in larger or more generalized samples. Studies focusing on chronic conditions or athletes (e.g., Yang *et al.* ⁵⁷, Tang *et al.* ⁵⁸, Zhu *et al.* ⁵⁹) emphasized proprioceptive recovery and joint function, influencing point selection accordingly.

6. Implications for clinical practice and future research

The findings from the reviewed studies affirm the clinical utility of acupuncture in the management of ankle sprains. There is consistent evidence supporting their efficacy in alleviating pain, improving joint function, and enhancing proprioception. These therapeutic benefits position acupuncture techniques as valuable tools in both acute and rehabilitative care.

The frequent selection of acupuncture points such as GB40, BL60, and ST41 highlights their potential role as foundational elements in treatment protocols for ankle sprains. This

trend may reflect a shared clinical consensus regarding their efficacy in addressing joint mobility, pain, and local circulation. Furthermore, the integration of *Ashi* points underscores a semi-standardized yet personalized treatment framework, allowing practitioners to tailor interventions based on individual patient presentations while maintaining consistency in therapeutic strategy.

Moreover, the application of adjunct techniques signals a growing interest in enhancing clinical outcomes through multimodal interventions. These combinations appear to support improved functional recovery, suggesting avenues for further exploration.

7. Conclusions

This review highlights the growing body of evidence supporting the use of acupuncture as an effective treatment modality for ankle sprains. Across diverse clinical settings, acupuncture consistently demonstrated benefits in pain relief, functional recovery, and proprioceptive enhancement. The strategic selection of local, distal, and *Ashi* points reflects both traditional principles and evolving clinical consensus. Integrating acupuncture into conventional musculoskeletal care may offer a valuable, individualized approach to both acute and chronic ankle sprain management. However, more high-quality studies are needed to support these findings.

Credit author statement: Conceptualization: R.T. and E.S.; Investigation: R.A., S.Q. A.S., R.C., and B.G.; Project Administration: R.T. and E.S.; Supervision: R.T. and E.S.; Writing – Original Draft Preparation: R.A., S.Q. A.S., R.C., and B.G.; Writing – Review & Editing: R.A., S.Q. A.S., R.C., B.G., R.T. and E.S. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: The original contributions presented in this study are included in the article. Further inquiries can be directed to the corresponding author.

References

1. Olds M, Ellis R, Parmar P, Kersten P. The immediate and subsequent impact of a first-time traumatic anterior shoulder dislocation in people aged 16–40: Results from a national cohort study. *Shoulder & Elbow*. 2020;13(2):223-32. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1758573220921484>
2. Marshall JL, Rubin RM. Knee Ligament Injuries—A Diagnostic and Therapeutic Approach. *Orthop Clin North Am*. 1977;8(3):641-68. doi: [https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/S0030-5898\(20\)30681-7](https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/S0030-5898(20)30681-7)
3. Tiefenboeck TM, Zeilinger J, Komjati M, Fialka C, Boesmueller S. Incidence, diagnostics and treatment algorithm of nerve lesions after traumatic shoulder dislocations: a retrospective multicenter study. *Arch Orthop Trauma Surg*. 2020;140(9):1175-80. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00402-020-03348-z>
4. Zhang Z, Zhang K-B, Mao B-N, Lai S-K, Li J, Fu W-L. The Effect of Irreducible Dislocation on Functional Outcomes in Knees With Multiligament Injuries: A Matched-Cohort Analysis. *Orthopaedic Journal of Sports Medicine*. 2020;8(8):2325967120940203. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1177/2325967120940203>
5. Walker RE, McDougall D, Patel S, Grant JA, Longino PD, Mohtadi NG. Radiologic review of knee dislocation: from diagnosis to repair. *AJR Am J Roentgenol*. 2013;201(3):483-95. doi: <https://doi.org/10.2214/ajr.12.10221>
6. Rubenstein LZ. Falls in older people: epidemiology, risk factors and strategies for prevention. *Age Ageing*. 2006;35 Suppl 2:ii37-ii41. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1093/ageing/afl084>

7. Burrus MT, Werner BC, Cancienne JM, Miller MD. Simultaneous bilateral multiligamentous knee injuries are associated with more severe multisystem trauma compared to unilateral injuries. *Knee Surg Sports Traumatol Arthrosc.* 2015;23(10):3038-43. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00167-015-3720-7>
8. Weber CD, Solomon LB, Lefering R, Horst K, Kobbe P, Hildebrand F, et al. Which Risk Factors Predict Knee Ligament Injuries in Severely Injured Patients?—Results from an International Multicenter Analysis. *Journal of clinical medicine.* 2020; 9(5). doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/jcm9051437>
9. Jacob Y, Anderton RS, Cochrane Wilkie JL, Rogalski B, Laws SM, Jones A, et al. Genetic variants within NOGGIN, COL1A1, COL5A1, and IGF2 are associated with musculoskeletal injuries in elite male Australian football league players: a preliminary study. *Sports medicine-open.* 2022;8(1):126.
10. Failla JM, Jacobson J, van Holsbeeck M. Ultrasound diagnosis and surgical pathology of the torn interosseous membrane in forearm fractures/dislocations. *The Journal of hand surgery.* 1999;24(2):257-66.
11. Peskun CJ, Levy BA, Fanelli GC, Stannard JP, Stuart MJ, MacDonald PB, et al. Diagnosis and Management of Knee Dislocations. *The Physician and Sportsmedicine.* 2010;38(4):101-11. doi: <https://doi.org/10.3810/psm.2010.12.1832>
12. Brooks RA, Ribbans WJ. Diagnosis and Imaging Studies of Traumatic Hip Dislocations in the Adult. *Clinical Orthopaedics and Related Research (1976-2007).* 2000;377.
13. Post M. Current Concepts in the Diagnosis and Management of Acromioclavicular Dislocations. *Clinical Orthopaedics and Related Research®.* 1985;200.
14. Bencardino JT, Rosenberg ZS, Brown RR, Hassankhani A, Lustrin ES, Beltran J. Traumatic Musculotendinous Injuries of the Knee: Diagnosis with MR Imaging. *Radiographics.* 2000;20(suppl_1):S103-S20. doi: https://doi.org/10.1148/radiographics.20.suppl_1.g00oc16s103
15. Waterman BR, Owens BD, Davey S, Zacchilli MA, Belmont PJ, Jr. The epidemiology of ankle sprains in the United States. *J Bone Joint Surg Am.* 2010;92(13):2279-84. doi: <https://doi.org/10.2106/jbjs.L01537>
16. Roos KG, Kerr ZY, Mauntel TC, Djoko A, Dompier TP, Wikstrom EA. The Epidemiology of Lateral Ligament Complex Ankle Sprains in National Collegiate Athletic Association Sports. *Am J Sports Med.* 2017;45(1):201-9. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0363546516660980>
17. Attenborough AS, Hiller CE, Smith RM, Stuelcken M, Greene A, Sinclair PJ. Chronic ankle instability in sporting populations. *Sports Med.* 2014;44(11):1545-56. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40279-014-0218-2>
18. Baydogan SN, Tarakci E, Kasapcopur O. Effect of strengthening versus balance-proprioceptive exercises on lower extremity function in patients with juvenile idiopathic arthritis: a randomized, single-blind clinical trial. *Am J Phys Med Rehabil.* 2015;94(6):417-24, quiz 25-8. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1097/phm.0000000000000279>
19. Taylor JB, Ford KR, Nguyen AD, Terry LN, Hegedus EJ. Prevention of Lower Extremity Injuries in Basketball: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *Sports Health.* 2015;7(5):392-8. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1941738115593441>
20. SantAnna JPC, Pedrinelli A, Hernandez AJ, Fernandes TL. Muscle injury: pathophysiology, diagnosis, and treatment. *Rev Bras Ortop.* 2022;57:1-13.
21. Palermi S, Massa B, Vecchiato M, Mazza F, De Blasiis P, Romano AM, et al. Indirect structural muscle injuries of lower limb: Rehabilitation and therapeutic exercise. *Journal of Functional Morphology and Kinesiology.* 2021;6(3):75.
22. Ishøi L, Krommes K, Husted RS, Juhl CB, Thorborg K. Diagnosis, prevention and treatment of common lower extremity muscle injuries in sport—grading the evidence: a statement paper commissioned by the Danish Society of Sports Physical Therapy (DSSF). *Br J Sports Med.* 2020;54(9):528-37.
23. Herzog MM, Kerr ZY, Marshall SW, Wikstrom EA. Epidemiology of Ankle Sprains and Chronic Ankle Instability. *J Athl Train.* 2019;54(6):603-10. doi: <https://doi.org/10.4085/1062-6050-447-17>

24. Ferreira CdS, Luz MT. Shen: categoria estruturante da racionalidade médica chinesa. *História, Ciências, Saúde-Manguinhos*. 2007;14.
25. Vieira MAM, Dzung TV. *Compêndio de Síndromes em Medicina Chinesa: Causa das Regras Associação*; 2014. 9789899825666.
26. Mattos DAC. *Guia prático de medicina chinesa*: Editora Alfabeta; 2019. 9788598307671.
27. Rodrigues JM, Mestre M, Fredes LI. Qigong in the treatment of children with autism spectrum disorder: A systematic review. *J Integr Med*. 2019;17(4):250-60. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joim.2019.04.003>
28. Matos LC, Machado JP, Monteiro FJ, Greten HJ. Understanding Traditional Chinese Medicine Therapeutics: An Overview of the Basics and Clinical Applications. *Healthcare (Basel, Switzerland)*. 2021;9(3). doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/healthcare9030257>
29. Cheung T. The difference and similarity between traditional chinese and western medicine. *Chin J Integr Tradit West Med*. 2000(1):68-70.
30. Rodrigues JM, Lopes L, Goncalves M, Machado JP. Taijiquan and qigong as a mindfulness cognitive-behavioural based therapy on the treatment of cothymia in school-age children - A preliminary study. *J Bodyw Mov Ther*. 2021;26:329-38. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbmt.2020.12.024>
31. Rodrigues JM, Lopes LT, Goncalves M, Machado JP. Perceived Health Benefits of Taijiquan and Qigong. *Altern Ther Health Med*. 2022;28(12).
32. Matos LC, Machado JP, Monteiro FJ, Greten HJ. Can Traditional Chinese Medicine Diagnosis Be Parameterized and Standardized? A Narrative Review. *Healthcare (Basel, Switzerland)*. 2021;9(2):177. doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/healthcare9020177>
33. Wang WY, Xie Y, Zhou H, Liu L. Contribution of traditional Chinese medicine to the treatment of COVID-19. *Phytomedicine : international journal of phytotherapy and phytopharmacology*. 2021;85:153279. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.phymed.2020.153279>
34. Yang Y, Islam MS, Wang J, Li Y, Chen X. Traditional Chinese Medicine in the Treatment of Patients Infected with 2019-New Coronavirus (SARS-CoV-2): A Review and Perspective. *Int J Biol Sci*. 2020;16(10):1708-17. doi: <https://doi.org/10.7150/ijbs.45538>
35. Ho LTF, Chan KKH, Chung VCH, Leung TH. Highlights of traditional Chinese medicine frontline expert advice in the China national guideline for COVID-19. *Eur J Integr Med*. 2020;36:101116. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eujim.2020.101116>
36. Bodeker G, Organization WH, Ong CK. *WHO Global Atlas of Traditional, Complementary and Alternative Medicine*: WHO Centre for Health Development; 2005. 9789241562867.
37. *Legal Status of Traditional Medicine and Complementary/Alternative Medicine: A Worldwide Review, I (2001)*.
38. World Health Organization. Traditional, complementary and integrative medicine [Available from: <http://www.who.int/traditional-complementary-integrative-medicine/en/>]
39. Santos C. New complementary approaches to anxiety treatment - A Narrative Review. *Journal of Complementary Therapies in Health*. 2023;1(2).
40. Simões K, Rodrigues JM. Acupuncture for erectile dysfunction: Insights and future research directions. *Revista Internacional de Acupuntura*. 2023;17(4). doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acu.2023.100269>
41. Rodrigues JM, Ventura C, Abreu M, Santos C, Monte J, Machado JP, et al. Electro-Acupuncture Effects Measured by Functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging-A Systematic Review of Randomized Clinical Trials. *Healthcare (Basel)*. 2023;12(1). doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/healthcare12010002>
42. Rodrigues JM, Santos C, Ribeiro V, Alvarenga A, Santos RV. Chinese Phytopharmacology in dermatology - A Systematic Review. *Pharmacological Research - Modern Chinese Medicine*. 2023;7:100255. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.prmcm.2023.100255>
43. Wen TS. *Acupuntura Clássica Chinesa*. Cultrix; 1985. p. 9-18. 9788531600029.
44. Rodrigues JM, Santos C, Ribeiro V, Silva A, Lopes L, Machado JP. Mental health benefits of traditional Chinese medicine – An umbrella review of meta-analyses. *Brain Behavior and Immunity Integrative*. 2023;2:100013. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbii.2023.100013>

45. Lee IS, Lee H, Chen YH, Chae Y. Bibliometric Analysis of Research Assessing the Use of Acupuncture for Pain Treatment Over the Past 20 Years. *J Pain Res.* 2020;13:367-76. doi: <https://doi.org/10.2147/JPR.S235047>
46. Liu B, Chen B, Guo Y, Tian L. Acupuncture – a national heritage of China to the world: international clinical research advances from the past decade. *Acupuncture and Herbal Medicine.* 2021;1(2).
47. Li R, Sun J, Hu H, Zhang Q, Sun R, Zhou S, et al. Research Trends of Acupuncture Therapy on Knee Osteoarthritis from 2010 to 2019: A Bibliometric Analysis. *Journal of Pain Research.* 2020;13:1901-13. doi: <https://doi.org/10.2147/JPR.S258739>
48. Zhu J, Li J, Yang L, Liu S. Acupuncture, from the ancient to the current. *The Anatomical Record.* 2021;304(11):2365-71. doi: <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1002/ar.24625>
49. Santos RV, Rodrigues JM, Jesus MI. Review on the effects of obesity treatment with acupuncture and phytoacupuncture. *World Journal of Acupuncture-Moxibustion.* 2020;30(3):223-8. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wjam.2020.07.002>
50. Altman S. Acupuncture therapy in small animal practice. *Compendium on Continuing Education for The Practicing Veterinarian.* 1997.
51. Liu A-F, Gong S-W, Chen J-X, Zhai J-B. Efficacy and Safety of Acupuncture Therapy for Patients with Acute Ankle Sprain: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis of Randomized Controlled Trials. *Evid Based Complement Alternat Med.* 2020;2020(1):9109531. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1155/2020/9109531>
52. Lu SW, Lang BX, Liu JN, Ma XX, Li TT, Du X, et al. Comparative Efficacy of Micro-Needle-Knife Therapy and Acupuncture in Acute Ankle Sprains: A Randomized Controlled Trial. *Med Sci Monit.* 2024;30:e944157. doi: <https://doi.org/10.12659/msm.944157>
53. Shin JC, Kim JH, Nam D, Park GC, Lee JS. Add-on effect of kinesiotape in patients with acute lateral ankle sprain: a randomized controlled trial. *Trials.* 2020;21(1):176. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13063-020-4111-z>
54. Du WB, Bao GA, Quan RF. [Impacts on analgesia and detumescence in ankle sprain treated with acupuncture at Xiaojie point combined with tendon-regulation manipulation]. *Zhongguo zhen jiu = Chinese acupuncture & moxibustion.* 2014;34(7):647-50.
55. Zhang ZX, Zhang BP, Guo KK, Miao P, Li SS, Wang RH. [Observation of the therapeutic effect on acute ankle sprain treated with surrounding needling and cold compression]. *Zhen ci yan jiu = Acupuncture research.* 2023;48(7):694-8. doi: <https://doi.org/10.13702/j.1000-0607.20220250>
56. Cohen MM, Smit V, Andrianopoulos N, Ben-Meir M, Taylor DM, Parker SJ, et al. Acupuncture for analgesia in the emergency department: a multicentre, randomised, equivalence and non-inferiority trial. *Med J Aust.* 2017;206(11):494-9. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5694/mja16.00771>
57. Yang Y, Liu J, Wang C, Zhao Y, Li N. [Effects of intradermal needling combined with tuina on ankle sprain sequelae]. *Zhongguo zhen jiu = Chinese acupuncture & moxibustion.* 2018;38(6):585-8. doi: <https://doi.org/10.13703/j.0255-2930.2018.06.004>
58. Tang WJ, Jiang CG, Chen LR, Pang Y, Li J, Huang Y. [Effects of acupuncture-moxibustion intervention on proprioception in athletes with lateral collateral ligament injury of ankle joint]. *Zhen ci yan jiu = Acupuncture research.* 2013;38(4):314-8.
59. Zhu Y, Qiu ML, Ding Y, Qiang Y, Qin BY. [Effects of electroacupuncture on the proprioception of athletes with functional ankle instability]. *Zhongguo zhen jiu = Chinese acupuncture & moxibustion.* 2012;32(6):503-6.
60. Park J, Hahn S, Park JY, Park HJ, Lee H. Acupuncture for ankle sprain: systematic review and meta-analysis. *BMC complementary and alternative medicine.* 2013;13:55. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1186/1472-6882-13-55>
61. Kim TH, Lee MS, Kim KH, Kang JW, Choi TY, Ernst E. Acupuncture for treating acute ankle sprains in adults. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev.* 2014;2014(6):Cd009065. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD009065.pub2>
62. Liu AF, Gong SW, Chen JX, Zhai JB. Efficacy and Safety of Acupuncture Therapy for Patients with Acute Ankle Sprain: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis of Randomized Controlled Trials. *Evidence-based complementary and alternative medicine : eCAM.* 2020;2020:9109531. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1155/2020/9109531>

63. Hu D, Sun H, Wang S, Wang H, Zheng X, Tang H, et al. Treatment and prevention of chronic ankle instability: An umbrella review of meta-analyses. *Foot Ankle Surg.* 2025;31(2):111-25. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fas.2024.07.010>
64. Melanson SW, Shuman VL. Acute ankle sprain. *StatPearls: StatPearls Publishing*; 2023.
65. Jiang S, Zhao J-s. The historical source of "Trigger Points": classical Ashi points. *World Journal of Acupuncture - Moxibustion.* 2016;26(2):11-4. doi: [https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/S1003-5257\(17\)30003-X](https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/S1003-5257(17)30003-X)
66. Lee S, Ryu Y, Lee I-S, Chae Y. Understanding the meaning and features of Ashi points. *Korean Journal of Acupuncture.* 2022;39(3):84-90.
67. Nugent-Head A. Ashi Points in Clinical Practice. *Journal of Chinese Medicine (JCM).* 2013(101).
68. Wang K-f, Zhang L-j, Lu F, Lu Y-h, Yang C-h. Can Ashi points stimulation have specific effects on shoulder pain? A systematic review of randomized controlled trials. *Chinese journal of integrative medicine.* 2016;22(6):467-72. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11655-015-2107-4>
69. Liang P, Wang Z, Qian T, Li K. Acupuncture Stimulation of Taichong (Liv3) and Hegu (LI4) Modulates the Default Mode Network Activity in Alzheimer's Disease. *American Journal of Alzheimer's Disease & Other Dementias®.* 2014;29(8):739-48. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1533317514536600>
70. Ji S, Zhang H, Qin W, Liu M, Zheng W, Han Y, et al. Effect of Acupuncture Stimulation of Hegu (LI4) and Taichong (LR3) on the Resting-State Networks in Alzheimer's Disease: Beyond the Default Mode Network. *Neural Plast.* 2021;2021:8876873. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1155/2021/8876873>
71. Jiang MC, Liang J, Zhang YJ, Wang JR, Hao JD, Wang MK, et al. [Effects of Acupuncture Stimulation of Bilateral "Hegu" (LI 4) and "Taichong" (LR 3) on Learning-memory Ability, Hippocampal AP 42 Expression and Inflammatory Cytokines in Rats with Alzheimer's Disease]. *Zhen ci yan jiu = Acupuncture research.* 2016;41(2):113-8.
72. Wang J, Bai X, Chen X, Liu S, Sun M, Li K, et al. Effects of acupuncture at the Taichong (LIV3) and Hegu (LI4) points on functional connectivity with the retrosplenial cortex in patients with Alzheimer's disease. *Frontiers in Neuroscience.* 2025;Volume 18 - 2024. doi: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnins.2024.1511183>
73. Chang KH, Bai SJ, Lee H, Lee BH. Effects of acupuncture stimulation at different acupoints on formalin-induced pain in rats. *The Korean Journal of Physiology & Pharmacology: Official Journal of the Korean Physiological Society and the Korean Society of Pharmacology.* 2014;18(2):121.
74. Marques CP. Análise eletromiográfica do músculo trapézio submetido a aplicação da acupuntura. 2012.
75. Silva MDd. Atividade antinociceptiva e inflamatória da acupuntura no acuponto spleen 6 (SP6) em camundongos: análise dos seus mecanismos neurobiológicos. 2013.
76. Ramires CC. Efeito da acupuntura nos transtornos de humor e memória induzidos por neuropatia periférica, associada ou não ao tratamento com gabapentina. 2019.
77. Liu B, Chen J, Wang J, Liu X, Duan X, Shang X, et al. Altered small-world efficiency of brain functional networks in acupuncture at ST36: a functional MRI study. *PloS one.* 2012;7(6):e39342.
78. Oliveira MBd. Efeito do acuponto ST36 na nocicepção induzida pela formalina e sua interação com o sistema histaminérgico. 2017.
79. Barcala TdS. Efeito antinociceptivo da estimulação manual do acuponto GB34 (Yanglingquan) no modelo experimental de dor muscular de início tardio em camundongos. 2014.
80. Yeo S, Lim S, Choe IH, Choi YG, Chung KC, Jahng GH, et al. Acupuncture Stimulation on GB 34 Activates Neural Responses Associated with Parkinson's Disease. *CNS neuroscience & therapeutics.* 2012;18(9):781-90.
81. Yeo S, Choe I-H, Van den Noort M, Bosch P, Jahng G-H, Rosen B, et al. Acupuncture on GB34 activates the precentral gyrus and prefrontal cortex in Parkinson's disease. *BMC complementary and alternative medicine.* 2014;14:1-9.

82. Campana AC, Aliberas JT, Blanco LA, Aragon MV, Cenador MBG. Contralateral acupuncture, a technique to be explored. Considerations on its neurophysiological mechanism. *Revista Internacional de Acupuntura*. 2024;18(1). doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acu.2024.100285>
83. Curran J. The Yellow Emperor's Classic of Internal Medicine. *BMJ*. 2008;336(7647):777. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.39527.472303.4E>
84. Chen S-q, Cai D-c, Chen J-x, Yang H, Liu L-s. Altered Brain Regional Homogeneity Following Contralateral Acupuncture at Quchi (LI 11) and Zusanli (ST 36) in Ischemic Stroke Patients with Left Hemiplegia: An fMRI Study. *Chinese journal of integrative medicine*. 2020;26(1):20-5. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11655-019-3079-6>
85. Yan C-Q, Huo J-W, Wang X, Zhou P, Zhang Y-N, Li J-L, et al. Different Degree Centrality Changes in the Brain after Acupuncture on Contralateral or Ipsilateral Acupoint in Patients with Chronic Shoulder Pain: A Resting-State fMRI Study. *Neural Plasticity*. 2020;2020(1):5701042. doi: <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1155/2020/5701042>
86. Rodrigues JM, Ventura C, Abreu M, Santos C, Monte J, Machado JP, et al. Electro-Acupuncture Effects Measured by Functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging—A Systematic Review of Randomized Clinical Trials. *Healthcare*. 2024;12(1). doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/healthcare12010002>
87. Tita G. The 'Surrounding the Dragon' (Wei Ci) Acupuncture Technique: A Systematic Review. *Journal of Chinese Medicine (JCM)*. 2024(135).
88. Wei Q-S, Wu J-L, Liang J, Qi M-H, Jiang F, Liu Y-X, et al. [Encircling needling is superior to "Bangci" (focal center-side needling) in promoting wound healing in diabetic mice]. *Zhen ci yan jiu = Acupuncture research*. 2020;45(5):373-8. doi: <https://doi.org/10.13702/j.1000-0607.190352>
89. Xu G, Zhou C-S, Tang W-Z, Xu J, Li X-L, Wei Q, et al. Neuroprotective effect of surround needling combined with acupoint injection on acute herpetic neuralgia. *Zhongguo Zhen jiu = Chinese Acupuncture & Moxibustion*. 2019;39(4):371-6.
90. Chu R. *Master Tung's Acupuncture Primer: An Introduction to the Master Tung Acupuncture System*: CreateSpace Independent Publishing Platform; 2015. 9781511754422.
91. Chu R. *The Best of Master Tung's Acupuncture: A Clinical Guide*: CreateSpace Independent Publishing Platform; 2015. 9781522756774.
92. Huang C, Sheu TW. Study of the effect of moxibustion on the blood flow. *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*. 2013;63:141-9.
93. Yang J, Min S, Xie F, Chen J, Hao X, Ren L. Electroacupuncture alleviates neuromuscular dysfunction in an experimental rat model of immobilization. *Oncotarget*. 2017;8(49):85537.
94. Yu R, Lu H, Hu X, Chen L, LV C, Zhang Y, et al. Electroacupuncture effect the neuromuscular functionality in rats with intensive care unit-acquired weakness. 2023.